

A Prospective Observational Study of Knee Synovitis

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ABSTRACT

Knee Synovitis is a inflammation of synovial membrane, which is connective tissue lining of the Knee joint. These disease is respond to the NSAID's, Steroids, DMARD's. The main aim of this study was to observe activities relating to the detection, prevention of complication or any medication related to the disease in a Nandi medical college and Research Institute, Chikkaballapur. This Prospective Observational study was conducted in out patient department. Among 150 cases, 16 cases was found under the age between 10-20(10.666666667%), 37 cases was found under the age between 21-40(24.666666667%), 56 cases was found under the age between 41-60(37.333333333%) and 41 cases was found under the age between 61-80(27.333333333%). Thus it was concluded that a Orthopedician can play a role in this situation, appears to be a strong intervention, early detection, prevention and thus can improve the quality of care of the patients. Educating the patient about the drug and their importance of right use. Literacy can be helpful in minimizing the complications of disease.

Keywords: Knee Synovitis, NSAID's-Non steroidal anti inflammatory drugs, DMARD's-Disease modifying anti rheumatic drugs, Arthritis, Knee joints, Synovial fluid.

INTRODUCTION

DEFINITION

Synovitis or Localized synovial membrane inflammation, is typically painful. It is characterized by joint swelling brought on by synovial thickening or effusion. Synovial inflammation is common following traumatic joint damage and is linked to enhanced pain and dysfunction ⁽¹⁾. It most likely happens when extracellular matrix macromolecules and broken pieces of cartilage enter the joint and come into touch with the synovium. When these fragments or molecules are released, synovial cells respond by activating and releasing inflammatory mediators ⁽²⁾. The Synovial membrane functions as the principle immunoreactive system of the joint. The primary immunoreactive system in a joint is the synovial membrane. Osteoarthritis and most auto immune diseases in bone include synovitis, an inflammation of the synovial membrane ⁽³⁾.

Synovium: The inside surface of synovial joint capsules is lined with a specialized connective soft tissue membrane known as synovium, also referred to as synovial membrane. In addition to bone, articular cartilage, ligaments, tendons, and a fibrous capsule, it is a crucial part of the tissue that makes up an integrated joint. As a result, it performs both structural and functional interactions with other tissues in the joints in addition to its own specific functions ⁽⁴⁾. The knee joint is the most often affected joint in synovial diseases and has the biggest reflection of the synovial lining. Infections, local proliferative diseases and systemic inflammatory arthritis are common chronic illnesses that affect the synovium ⁽⁵⁾. **Synovial fluid** lubricates articular cartilage and supplies nutrition and it is composed of an ultrafiltrate of blood plasma that the synovium produces and controls ⁽⁶⁾. A region of the synovial compartment with thickness larger than the typical synovium's breadth and above-normal gadolinium enhancement. Two milliliters of synovial fluid are present in a healthy knee ⁽⁷⁾.

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The **Synovial tissue** is a primary target of multiple disease characterized by different pathogenic mechanisms, including infective, deposition, neoplastic and chronic immune inflammatory pathologies. It keeps the articular joint well lubricated and it also provides nutrients to the articular surface⁽⁸⁾. **Synovial joints** are the body's most prevalent kind of joints. These joints can move freely and Synovial joints that is not seen at fibrous or cartilaginous joints in presence of a joint cavity. The synovial membrane, or synovium, which lines the articular capsule, secretes synovial fluid, which is found in the joint cavity⁽⁹⁾.

There are Six types of synovial joints are :-

- Hinge (Elbow, Knee)
- Saddle (Carpometacarpal joint)
- Planar (acromioclavicular joint)
- Pivot (atlantoaxial joint)
- Condylloid (metacarpophalangeal joint)
- Ball and socket (Hip joint)

1.2 TYPES OF SYNOVITIS

- a) Acute Synovitis
- b) Chronic Synovitis
- c) Reactive Synovitis
- d) Post-traumatic Synovitis

a) ACUTE SYNOVITIS: This type of Synovitis causes the joint volume to increase for a few hours to entire day. The shape and contour of the knee may change. It often comes along with an increased body temperature, joint restriction and pain.

b) CHRONIC SYNOVITIS: Another form of synovitis, chronic synovitis is not as common as acute synovitis. It often comes along with weariness when walking or painful pain and discomfort.

c) REACTIVE SYNOVITIS: A type of synovitis producing an increase in the volume of fluid in the

d) joint, reactive synovitis generally causes limited mobility. It's not a common type of synovitis and often arises when something else is present, such as an allergic reaction.

e) POST-TRAUMATIC SYNOVITIS: Cuts, abrasions or other injuries result in post-traumatic synovitis, the most prevalent kind of synovitis. The body responds damage to the synovium by producing discomfort and edema^(10,11).

1.3 GRADING OF KNEE SYNOVITIS

Knee Synovitis can be graded according to a scale of 0-3⁽¹²⁾

- Grade 0
- Grade 1
- Grade 2
- Grade 3

GRADE	CONDITION
Grade 0	There is no Synovial Thickening.
Grade 1	There is minimal Synovial Thickening without bluging over the tops of the bones.
Grade 2	There is more extensive Synovial Thickening with blugins over the tops of the periatricular bones.
Grade 3	More extensive thickening with extension beyond the joint .

1.4 EITIOLOGY OF KNEE SYNOVITIS

Knee Synovitis is usually a secondary condition. Possible causes include:

- ✓ Knee injuries.
- ✓ Overuse syndrome.
- ✓ Infection in the joint.
- ✓ Gout - This is a painful condition affecting joints.
- ✓ Cancer – It is important that if you have synovitis then it is investigated properly.
- ✓ Autoimmune disorder.
- ✓ Traumas like falls and car accidents.
- ✓ Repetitive strain injuries.
- ✓ Sports injuries.
- ✓ Ankylosing spondylitis and systemic lupus erythematosus
- ✓ Allergic reactions ⁽¹²⁾ .

1.5 CLINICAL MANIFESTATION

Signs and Symptoms of Synovitis depend on what area of the body is affected. Typically, most people with Knee Synovitis will experience these Symptoms:

- ❖ Arthralgia
- ❖ Swelling
- ❖ Difficulty moving the affected area
- ❖ Thickening of the tissue

❖ Increased blood flow to the affected area

❖ Increased fluid production

❖ Redness

❖ Stiffness

❖ Feels puffy or boggy to touch

❖ Tenderness

❖ Fever (Over 102* F)

1.6 RISK FACTORS

❖ Aging

❖ Chronic medical problem

❖ Repetitive Sports or activitis with Repetitive use of a same joint

❖ Improper posture

❖ Getting an infection that can spread to bursae, bones and joints

❖ Injuries to the bursae

❖ People with autoimmune disorders

❖ People who do manual labor

1.7 COMPLICATIONS

Complications associated with Knee Synovial diseases include:

❖ **Excruciating pain** : The pain may get unbearable with time and if left untreated.

- ❖ **FEVER** : When the inflammation worsens the patient may come with fever.
- ❖ **Arthritis** : Synovial diseases are often related to various forms of arthritis. If not treated on time, they lead to arthritis.
- ❖ Recurrence of symptoms

- ❖ Joint deformities
- ❖ The anti-inflammatory medication doesn't start working

1.8 PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

➤ KNEE SYNOVITIS IN OSTEOARTHRITIS

The pathophysiology of osteoarthritis (OA) involves the synovium; activated synovial cells in the inflammatory synovium release catabolic and pro-inflammatory mediators, which in turn cause an overproduction of the proteolytic enzymes that break down cartilage. Synovial cells phagocytose byproducts of cartilage degradation that are discharged into the synovial fluid, hence exacerbating synovial inflammation. The inflammatory response is augmented by invading macrophages, activated synovial T cells, and B cells. To counteract this inflammatory reaction, anti-inflammatory cytokines may be released by the cartilage and synovium. In addition to its effects on inflammation and cartilage deterioration, the inflammatory synovium uses BMPs to contribute to the production of osteophytes. The growth factors released are BMP (bone morphogenetic protein), CXCL13 (CXC-chemokine ligand 13), ADAMTS (a disintegrin and metalloproteinase with thrombospondin domains) and EGF endothelial growth factor, interleukin, IL – 1Ra antagonist of the IL – 1 receptor, leukotriene B4, MMP matrix metalloproteinase, NAMPT (nicotinamide phosphoribosyl transferase), NO (nitric oxide), OA, prostaglandin E2, TIMP tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinase, TNF (tumor necrosis factor), VCAM – 1 (vascular cell adhesion molecule 1) and VEGF (vascular endothelial growth factor) ⁽¹³⁾.

1.9 DIAGNOSIS: In order to make a Knee synovitis diagnosis, a doctor must be aware of the patient's

symptoms, medical history and physical examination results ⁽¹⁴⁾. Additionally, the physician could request diagnostic testing like Studies on synovial fluid that are physical (MRI, CT scan, x-ray), biochemical and microbiological tests have shown to be helpful additions to the diagnosis. They do not have good predictive values or specificity ⁽¹⁵⁾. A synovial biopsy plus synovial fluid testing and synovial fluid analysis improves the diagnostic potential. Often, a needle biopsy will not yield representative diseased tissue ⁽¹⁶⁾. In addition, a visual examination of the joint can be used to detect a pattern of synovial growth. If necessary, further procedures such a synovectomy or micro fracture for cartilage abnormalities can be performed concurrently ⁽⁵⁾.

- ❖ **Arthroscopy and Synovial biopsy of Knee:-**A local anesthetic was used for the arthroscopy procedure, which is a safe and well-tolerated method. First, 2.7 mm diameter needle arthroscopy was inserted into the knee joint through an inferolateral portal, exploring all three articular compartments. Afterwards, a thorough intra-articular examination was conducted and a superolateral portal was used to obtain the biopsy specimens. The biopsy specimens were taken under direct visualization from areas of macroscopically apparent synovial villous hypertrophy, snap frozen in optimal cutting temperature (OCT) embedding medium by

submerging them in liquid nitrogen, and kept at -70°C until further processing.

- ❖ **Knee Synovial cell cultures:** Tissue samples from patients with early and late OA were minced and they were incubated for two hours with 4 microgram per ml collagenase type 2 in culture RPMI 1640 medium with L-glutamine. Following centrifugation, the cells were plated in 25 cm² culture flasks and grown in medium supplemented with 1 M HEPES buffer + 20% fetal calf serum + penicillin (100 U/ml) + 2500 microgram per ml amphotericin B at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere of 95% air/5% CO₂ are added and diagnosed⁽¹⁷⁾.

1.10 MANAGEMENT OF KNEE SYNOVITIS:-

Pharmacotherapy is the use of medications to treat a medical condition is an important part of having the therapy of (Knee Synovitis). The goal of pharmacotherapy for Knee Synovitis is to reduce the joint pain and to reduce the risk of recurrent symptoms. The choice of medication, type, severity of the symptoms and the patients overall health.

1) FIRST-LINE KNEE SYNOVITIS TREATMENT:-

Treatments for Knee Synovitis center on reducing symptoms and managing any underlying health disorders that drive Knee inflammation.

- Non-steroidal anti-inflammatories (NSAIDs) like Advil or Motrin (ibuprofen), diclofenac are typically given for the first to reduce pain and inflammation.

2) OTHER TREATMENTS INCLUDE:-

- Draining the fluid that is built up in the Knee.
- Disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) to manage inflammatory causes. Ex:- Methotrexate
- Steroid injections to reduce swelling and pain. Ex-Corticosteroids (Prednisolone)
- Antibiotics: - This are mainly used to treat the Knee inflammations. Ex-Amoxicillin

- Proton pump inhibitors :- To prevent acid reflux
Ex- Pantoprazole
- H₂ inhibitors :-To relieve the symptoms of acid reflux
Ex- Ranitidine

3) COMPLIMENTARY THERAPIES:-

Although there isn't much scientific data supporting alternative therapy for knee synovitis, some of them could be able to lessen discomfort and swelling while you take other drugs or look into other medical options. A few choices are as follows:

- Using ice or heat therapy
- Knee Compression
- Wearing Knee braces, bandages, tapes and sleeves
- Knee resting

4) SURGICAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR KNEE SYNOVITIS:-

You could need to have surgery or think about complementary therapies in addition to first-line treatments, if first-line medications are ineffective for your knee synovitis in order to further relieve symptoms. If medications and other therapies do not work for knee synovitis and you continue to experience worsened pain and inflammation, your healthcare provider may recommend a surgery known as **synovectomy**. The surgery removes the synovium entirely. There are two types of synovectomy: arthroscopic and open. An arthroscopic procedure is less invasive than open. According to studies, both types of surgery have similar results. Both surgeries provide pain relief by following the procedure⁽¹⁸⁾.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN:

It is a prospective Observational Study.

STUDY LOCATION: The study was conducted in the outpatient counseling department in a Nandi

Medical College and Research Institute
Chikkaballapura.

STUDY SIZE: 150 patients.

STUDY DURATION: 6 Months.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Both genders were taken into the age group of 10-80 years.
- Diagnosed patients and the subjects willing to perform in this study.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- We excluded critically ill patients, who are unable to communicate verbally
- We excluded patients, who are afraid to participate in the study

STUDY PROCEDURE:

- Prospectively select the patients by random sampling.
- Patients further divided according to their age group.
- Then the patients are categorized according to their disease stage condition.
- Risk factors, symptoms, causes and complications of Knee synovitis had identified.

CLINICAL OUTCOMES:

- Assessment of risk and complications in the subjects.
- Lifestyle modifications for Knee synovitis outcome.
- To decrease risk and complications of Knee synovitis, use appropriate medications.

STATISTICAL PLAN:

- The statistical analysis was carried out by Microsoft Office (MS Word, MS Excel, and Graph pad Prism 8)
- Descriptive data analysis had performed in a percentage form of demographic variables

3] RESULTS

3.1 AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION OF KNEE SYNOVITIS

We assessed the 10-80 years age group of patients suffering from Knee Synovitis. We have graded the age group into four levels. It includes age groups of 10-20, 21-40, 41-60, 61-80 years. Among 150 patients, we found 16 patients under the age group of 10-20 years, 37 patients under the age group between 21-40 years, 56 patients under the age group between 41-60 years, 41 patients under the age group between 61-80 years. Under the age of 41-60 years, we found maximum number of Knee Synovitis patients was 56. The results had given in table 3.1 and figure 3.1

Table no and Figure 3.1: Age distribution of Knee Synovitis patients

SL.No	Age	Number of patients	Percentage%
1	10-20	16	10.666666667
2	21-40	37	24.666666667
3	41-60	56	37.333333333
4	61-80	41	27.333333333
	Total	N=150	100

Name: - Premsagar

Age :- 12Y (10-20)

Name: - Sayed Kairoj

Age :- 35Y (21-40)

Name :- Narasamma

Age :- 55Y (41-60)

Name :- Shanthamma

Age :- 78Y (61-80)

3.2 GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF SYNOVITIS PATIENTS:

Among 150 patients we found that 92 patients were males and 58 patients are females. In this study males

were more prone to develop Knee Synovitis than female. The results had given in table 3.2 and figure 3.2 .

Table no and Figure no 3.2: Gender of Knee Synovitis

z	Gender	Number of patients	Percentage%
1	Male	92	61.333333333
2	Female	58	38.666666667
	Total	N=150	100

3.3 RISK FACTORS OF KNEE SYNOVITIS:

In this study, out of 150 patients 36 patients have aging, 19 patients have arthritis, 67 patients have

people who do manual labour and 28 patients have injuries to the bursae. The result had given in the table 3.3 and figure 3.3.

Table and figure no 3.3: Risk factors of Synovitis patients

SL.No	Risk Factors	Number of patients	Percentage%
1	Aging	36	24
2	Arthritis	19	12.666666667
3	People who do manual labor	67	44.666666667
4	Injuries to the bursae	28	18.666666667
	Total	N=150	100

3.4 SYMPTOMS OF KNEE SYNOVITIS PATIENTS:

In this study, among 150 patients, 123 patients had symptoms like stiffness, 150 patients had swelling, 150 patients had knee pain, 77 patients had redness,

123 patients had numbness, 115 patients had joint pain during walking, 52 patients had joint effusion, 115 patients had puffy feeling while touch, 77 patients had tenderness, 115 patients had fever. The results had given in table 3.4 and figure 3.4 .

Table and Figure no 3.4 Symptoms of Knee Synovitis patients

SL.No	Symptoms	Number of patients	Percentage%
1	Stiffness	123	82
2	Swelling	150	100
3	Knee pain	150	100
4	Redness	77	51.333333333
5	Numbness	123	82
6	Joint pain during walking	115	76.666666667
7	Joint effusion	52	34.666666667
8	Feel puffy while touch	115	76.666666667
9	Tenderness	77	51.333333333
10	Fever	115	76.666666667

3.5 COMPLICATIONS OF KNEE SYNOVITIS PATIENTS:

patients had arthritis and 109 patients don't have any complications. This results had given in table 3.5 and figure 3.5.

In our study, out of 150 patients only 22 patients had complications that is recurrence of symptoms, 19

Table and figure no 3.5: Categories of drugs for Knee Synovitis patients

SL.No	Complication	Number of patients	Percentage%
1	Arthritis	19	12.666666667
2	Recurrence of Symptoms	22	14.666666667
3	No	109	72.666666667
	Total	N=150	100

3.6 CATEGORIES OF THE DRUGS PRESCRIBED IN KNEE SYNOVITIS PATIENTS:

pump inhibitors, DMARD'S, Anti-inflammatory, steroids. The results had given in table 3.6 and figure 3.6 .

Out of 150 patients, maximum number of patients prescribed the category of drugs like antibiotic, proton

Table and figure no 3.6: Categories of drugs for Knee Synovitis patients

SL.No	Category	Number of patients	Percentage%
1	Antibiotics	37	24.666666667
2	Proton pump inhibitors	143	95.333333333
3	DMARD's	7	4.666666667

4	Anti-inflammatory	71	47.33333333
5	Steroids	33	22
6	H ₂ inhibitor	7	4.666666667

3.7 PRESCRIBED DRUGS IN KNEE SYNOVITIS PATIENTS:

Diclofenac, Ibuprofen, Pantoprazole, Zerodol SP, Tylenol, Prednisone, paracetamol, Methotrexate, Ranitidine. The results had given in table 3.7 and figure 3.7 .

In this study, out of 150 cases the drugs prescribed for Knee Synovitis includes Amoxicillin, Calcium,

Table and figure no 3.7: Drugs Prescribed For Knee Synovitis patients

SL.No	Drugs Name	Number of Pateints	Percentage%
1	Amoxicillin (500mg)	37	24.66666667
2	Calcium (500mg)	137	91.33333333
3	Diclofenac (50mg)	12	8
4	Ibuprofen (400mg)	14	9.333333333
5	Pantoprazole (40mg)	143	95.33333333
6	Zerodol sp (500mg)	15	10
7	Tylenol (500mg)	14	9.333333333
8	Prednisolone (5mg)	33	22
9	Paracetamol (650mg)	16	10.66666667
10	Methotrexate (7.5mg)	7	4.666666667
11	Folic acid(5mg)	7	4.666666667
12	Ranitidine (150mg)	7	4.666666667

3.8 Distribution of Knee Synovitis patients based on history:

Out of 150 subjects based on history we observed that 11 patients are between 1 – 2 weeks, 42 patients are

between 1 – 5 months and 97 patients are between 6 – 12 months . Most subjects are found in between 6 – 12 months. The results had given in table 3.8 and figure 3.8 .

Table and figure no 3.8 Distribution of Knee Synovitis patients based on History

SL.No	History	Number of patients	Percentage%
1	1 - 2 week	11	7.3333333333
2	1 - 5months	42	28
3	6-12months	97	64.666666667
		N=150	100

3.9 Number of drugs per prescription for Knee Synovitis patients:

As per our study, out of 150 subjects 24 subjects prescribed by 2 number of drugs per prescription, 95

subjects prescribed by 3 number of drugs per prescription and 31 subjects prescribed by 4 number of drugs per prescription. The results had given in table 3.9 and figure 3.9.

Table and figure no 3.9 Number of drugs per prescription for Knee Synovitis patients:

SL.No	Number of drugs per prescription	Number of patients	Percentage%
1.	2	24	16
2.	3	95	63.333333333
3.	4	31	20.666666667
Total	9	N=150	100

DISCUSSION

We had done a study among 150 Knee Synovitis cases in the Chikkaballapur Nandi Medical College and Research Institute. In our study, we observed the patients under age group of 41-60(37.33333333%) years were acquired to develop Knee Synovitis. Our study tells the details of the maximum prevalence 56(37.33333333%) in the age category of 41-60 years. In our study both males and females affected by Knee Synovitis, males are more commonly affected from Knee Synovitis than females because, due to the fact that males overuse their Knee joints and perform more work than females. Males cases were 92(61.33333333%) and females 58(38.66666667%). On occasion, the over production of inflammatory mediators might also exacerbate knee inflammation. In our study the maximum number of patients shows the primary symptoms. In our study, the maximum patients don't have complications and some patients having arthritis problem and recurrence of symptoms and physician should provide precautions to the patients like "Take rest between making the same motions over and over again" In our study the maximum number of patients are suffering from 6 – 12 months, Because Knee Synovitis is a chronic condition. We cannot cure the disease but we can reduce the severity of symptoms. By depending on the patient condition and degree of illness, medical treatment had given to the each and every patient. Generally the therapy will start after the diagnosis of the disease. Other treatments like Steroids (prednisolone-5mg) prescribed once a day, which reduces inflammation and knee pain. In our study, the concerned data collection parameters like aging, arthritis, people who do manual labor and injuries to bursae act as a major risk factor in the formation of Knee Synovitis. Its mechanism of action is to inhibit inflammation. Methotrexate is prescribed with folic acid drugs.

CONCLUSION

➤ According to our study, Knee Synovitis occurs mainly due to overuse of Knee, trauma, sports injury, knee injury, Auto immune disorder and infection in the joint. 41-60 years of age group individuals are more prone to develop knee synovitis. Males have greater risk than females in

developing knee synovitis. As per our study, Knee Synovitis occurs due to age, Injury to the bursae, arthritis and People who do manual labor.

➤ "Take rest between making the same motions over and over again". The maximum patients don't have complications but some patients having arthritis problem and recurrence of symptoms and physician should provide precautions to the patients. We suggest that the patients suffering from Knee Synovitis should avoid foods like, Red meat, Saturated fats, Refined grains, excessive Sugar and Salt. The patients should take foods like, Oily fish, Dark leafy vegetables, nuts and seeds, anti-oxidants, dry fruits and egg.

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